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LEAFROLLERS FROM THE TRIBES BACTRINI AND ENDOTHEINIINI FROM THE
SOUTHEASTERN REGION OF ABKHAZIA (GEORGIA)

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Abstract. In 1985–1988, as part of an expedition conducted in the southeastern region of Abkhazia, specimens were collected from the local fauna, specifically the representatives of the family Tortricidae (Lepidoptera), which were subsequently studied at the Insect Systematics Laboratory of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences in Saint Petersburg. Particular attention was given to two genera from the tribes Bactrini and Endotheniini. A total of 5 species were identified from the genus *Bactra*, and 4 species from the genus *Endothenia*. The final identification of the species was based on their genital structure. It is confirmed that the vast majority of recorded species are monocyclic, with their imago flying in July. Exceptions are two species – *Endothenia genthianaeana* and *Endothenia carbonana* – whose imagos are observed to fly from June to September. Specimens of the species found in the region are stored in the stock collections of the Zoological Institute of Saint Petersburg.

Keywords: Species, Genus, Genital Structures, Identification, Diagnostics, Expedition, Imago, Larva.

აფხაზეთის სამხრეთ-აღმოსავლეთ რეგიონის ფოთოლხვევიები ტრიბებიდან
Bactrini და *Endotheniini* (საქართველო)

გიორგი ფარულავა

პროფესორი, ბიოლოგიის მეცნიერებათა დოქტორი, საქართველოს ფიზიკური აღზრდისა და სპორტის სახელმწიფო სასწავლო უნივერსიტეტი;
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აბსტრაქტი. 1985-1988 წლებში აფხაზეთის სამხრეთ-აღმოსავლეთ რეგიონში ჩატარებული ექსპედიციის ფარგლებში შეგროვებულიქნა ფაუნისტური მასალა, მათ შორის ფოთოლხვევიების (Lepidoptera, Tortricidae) ოჯახის წარმომადგენლები, რომელიც დამუშავებულიქნა რუსეთის მეცნიერებათა აკადემიის სანკტ-პეტერბურგის ზოოლოგიური ინსტიტუტის მწერების სისტემატიკის ლაბორატორიაში. ყურადღება მიიპყრო ზემოთაღნიშნული ოჯახის ორმა გვარმა ტრიბებიდან *Bactrini* და *Endotheniini*. გვარიდან *Bactra* იდენტიფიცირებულია 5 სახეობა, გვარიდან *Endothenia* კი 4 სახეობა. სახეობათა საბოლოო დიაგნოსტიკა ჩატარდა გენიტალური სტრუქტურის აგებულების მიხედვით. დადასტურებულია, რომ აღრიცხულ სახეობათა დიდი უმრავლესობა მონოციკლურია, მათი იმაგო დაფრინავს ივლისში. გამონაკლისს წარმოადგენს ორი სახეობა - *Endothenia genthianaeana* Hb. და *Endothenia carbonana* Dbld. რომლის იმაგოს ფრენა აღინიშნება ივნისიდან სექტემბრის ჩათვლით. აღნიშნულ რეგიონში აღმოჩენილ

სახეობათა ნიმუშები ინახება სანკტ-პეტერბურგის ზოოლოგიური ინსტიტუტის საფონდო კოლექციებში.

Introduction. In 1985–88, an expedition was conducted across Georgia to study leafrollers, organized by the St. Petersburg Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The southeastern region of Abkhazia, which includes the Ochamchire and Gali districts, was the focus of our research. Both Gali and Ochamchire are coastal regions. Gali is bordered to the east by Tsalenjikha district, to the south by Zugdidi district, to the west by the Black Sea, and to the north by Ochamchire district. It was in these areas that the data were collected for further research and diagnosis [1].

Goals. The discovery of representatives from two tribes, **Bactrini** and **Endotheniini**, within the family of leafrollers, and the analysis of the collected data. A tribe is a taxonomic rank used to group genera that share certain common characteristics. It is positioned below the family level but above the genus level and is widely used in the classification of the order Lepidoptera.

Objectives. Laboratory processing and faunistic-systematic analysis of leafrollers collected in the mentioned region.

Materials and methods. In the field, during expeditions, Imagos were collected at night, from 9:00 PM to 2:00 AM, by setting up a DRL lamp near the screen. Occasionally, a quartz light source (PRK-2 lamp) was used. The collected material was processed at the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, in the so-called ZIN laboratory. For morphological analysis and the identification of distinguishing features, a binocular-stereoscopic microscope was employed. Genital structures were treated with a 10% KOH solution, and their drawings were made using the Gorodkov drawing tool [2]. The processed specimens were compared for identification with collections from Asia and Europe [3]. The final determination of the taxa was based on the genital structure, with references from V. Kuznetsov, A. Danilevsky, and G. Parulava [4, 5, 6].

Discussion and Results: It is well-known that the coastal region is relatively poor in terms of fauna, as the sea acts as a significant barrier to the spread of fauna, serving as an isolating factor. However, in the study area, this factor is partially compensated by the presence of Colchian forest thickets and impenetrable shrublands. In settled areas, compensation is further provided by orchards and agricultural plantings. Additionally, cultural landscapes are extensively represented by vineyards, vegetable gardens, and crops such as tea, tobacco, citrus, and others [7].

As part of the broader study of leafrollers across Georgia, specimens were collected from the southeastern part of Abkhazia, specifically covering two administrative units: The Ochamchire and Gali [18, 19] districts. The diagnostic analysis of the collected and labeled material revealed that two tribes deserve special attention. From the tribe **Bactrini**, the following species from the genus **Bactra** (Figure A) were identified:

> **Bactra lancealana** Hbn.

(Kuznetsov, 1978; Parulava, 1987).

This species is widespread, it was recorded for the first time in the fauna of Georgia. Its larvae are found on the stems and leaves of herbaceous plants.

The imago, with fully extended wings, measures 14–18 mm. They fly in the second half of July.

Specimens were found in the surroundings of Otobaya (1 specimen) and near the Zugdidi Botanical Garden (2 specimens) in 1990. (G. Parulava).

Complete scheme of genital structures, in accordance with V. Kuznetsov.

Figure A. *Bactra* Stph.

Figure 1.

Explanations of the inscriptions on the male genitals shown in the Picture: Соц - socii; эд-edeagus; к- caulis; ю - juxta; Верш. Эд- Apex of the edeagus; сакк. - saccus; верш. Сакк – Apex of the saccus; кук - cucullus; верш.влв – Apex of the valva; баз.о – basal outgrowth; тег - tegumen.

The following species have been identified from the genus *Bactra* Stph. [13, 14, 15,] :

> ***Bactra furfurana* Hw.**

(Pirce, Metkalfе, 1922; Кузнецов, 1978; Bradley, Tremevan, Smith, Hargreaves, 1979; Парулава, 1987).

It is widespread everywhere, including in the Caucasus, nevertheless, it is a new species for the fauna of Georgia. Its larvae develop on the stems of herbaceous plants.

Imago with wingspan is 13-18 mm, flies in July.

Specimens were found in the vicinity of Agubedia Monastery (2 specimens) and in Lagodekhi (2 specimens) in 1986-1987 (G. Parulava).

Genital structure is given in Figure 2.

> ***Bactra lacteana* Car.**

(Kuznetsov, 1975, 1978; Parulava, 1987)

It is widespread everywhere, except for the northern regions, nevertheless it is a new species for the fauna of the Caucasus and Georgia. The Larvae probably feed on grain plants, the nutrient plant for Georgia's conditions needs to be determined.

Imago with wingspan is 13-17 mm, flies in July.

Specimens were found in the vicinity of Agubedia (1 specimen) and in the Lagodekhi nature reserve (2 specimens) 1986-1987. (G. Parulava).

Genital structure, Figure 3.

> **Bactra bactrana Kenn.**

(Kuznetsov, 1975, 1978; Parulava, 1987)

It is a widespread species, but it is new for the fauna of Georgia. Its larvae feed on legume stems. The imago with the wings spread is 12-15 mm. They fly in July.

Specimens were collected in the vicinity of Bedia, 1987. (G. Parulava)

The genital structure is shown in Figure 4.

> **Bactra robustana Chr.**

(Kennel, 1908; Kuznetsov, 1978; Bradlei, Tremevan, Smith, Hargreaves, 1979; Parulava, 1987)

It is a widespread species, but it has not been found in the Caucasus, it is new for the fauna of the South Caucasus. Its larvae feed on cane (especially *Scirpus maritimus*) stems and roots.

The imago with the wings spread is 14-20 mm. They fly in July. In Georgia, 2 specimens were collected in Bedia area and 2 specimens in Lagodekhi nature reserve, 1986-1987 (G. Parulava).

Genital structure is given in Figure 5.

From the tribe Endotherniini, *Endothernia* Stph was recorded in the same region. (Figure B). The following species of the genus [16, 17] :

> **Endothernia marginana Hw.**

(Kennel, 1908; Pirce, Metkalf, 1922; Kuznetsov, 1978; Parulava, 1987).

It is a widespread species, inhabiting everywhere across the entire Palaearctic. The larvae develop on composite and labiates plants. The imago has a wingspan of 12-16 mm. It flies in June and July. Specimens were collected in Georgia: 3 specimens in the vicinity of the village of Tagiloni, 8 specimens in Dikhasurga, and 38 specimens in Lagodekhi, between 1985 and 1987 (G. Parulava) Genital structure is given in figure B (6).

Figure B (6)

Definitions of genital inscriptions are given under Figure A.

> ***Endothenia genthianaeana* Hb.**

(Kennel, 1908; Spuler, 1910; Kuznetsov, 1978; Bradley, Tremevan, Smith, Hargreaves, 1979; Parulava, 1987).

This species is widespread everywhere, it is recorded in almost all regions of Georgia. Carnivorous larvae develop in the flower stalks of tea trees, carnations and other similar plants.

The imago with the wings spread is 12-19 mm. They fly from the end of June to September.

7 specimens were found in Tagilons, 3 in Saberio, 48 in the rest of Georgia.

Genital structure is given in Figure 7.

> ***Endothenia nigricostana* Hw.**

(Kennel, 1908; Pirce, Metkalf, 1922; Kuznetsov, 1978; Parulava, 1987)

It is a new species for the fauna of the entire Caucasus, including Georgia. Its larvae develop on the stems and roots of smallpox plants.

Imago with wings spread 9-14 mm, flies in August.

3 specimens were found in Dikhazurga, 9 in the rest of Georgia.

Genital structure is given in Figure 8.

> ***Endothenia carbonana* Dbld.**

(Pierce, Metkalf, 1922; Kuznetsov, 1978; Parulava, 1987).

It is a new species for the fauna of Georgia. Its larvae grow on soft ivy.

Imago with spread wings is 10-14 mm, flies from June to September. 2 specimens were found in the vicinity of Okhurei, 107 specimens were found in the rest of Georgia.

Genital structure is given in Figure 9.

Figure A. Bactra.

Fig. 2

Fig.3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig.A. Bactra Stph.

2. *B. furfurana* Hw. 3. *B. lacteana* Car. 4. *B. Bactrana* Kenn. 5 *B. robustana* Chr.

Fig. B. Endothenia.

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. B. Endothenia Stph.

7. – *E. gentianaena* Hb. 8.- *E. nigricostana* Hw. 9. – *E. carbonana* Dbld.

Conclusion

An analysis of the specimens collected from the southeastern region of Abkhazia, specifically from the Ochamchire and Gali districts, revealed that the genus **Bactra** (Bactrini) of the family **Tortricidae** (Lepidoptera) consists of 5 species, while the genus **Endothenia** (Endotheniini) is represented by 4 known species. The species of the genus **Bactra** differ from each other based on the shape of the valva parts of the male genital structure. The species of the genus **Endothenia**, on the other hand, can be distinguished and accurately diagnosed by the shape and size of both the valva and the edeagus. All nine recorded species are important from both a faunistic standpoint and in terms of their relevance to agriculture and forestry.

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